

Analysis of Judo Wrestling Techniques Classification

Norov Yuldosh Beknazarovich¹

¹ Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, "Physical culture" department associate, professor

Abstract:

This thesis examines the peculiarities of the classification of the Japanese school of judo wrestling, the volume of technique and its content, which is an attempt to create a multi-level classification scheme. Due to the lack of a systematic classification and limited technical techniques, they cannot replace what in classification theory is called the key to constructing names.

Keywords: classification of technique, art of throws, twist throws, volume of technique.

INTRODUCTION.

It is well known that judo wrestling existed in Japan for many centuries before a centralized judo school (Kodokan) was formed at the end of the century before last. The period preceding this is characterized by the fact that in Japan there were numerous private schools, teaching in which and the training of the teachers themselves were carried out in a closed family circle of a given surname. Each private school used its own pedagogical techniques and, of course, used its own terminology. These family schools competed with each other and passed on teaching methods directly from generation to generation under the strictest confidence.

The Kodokan School in Japan played a very progressive role by uniting all the schools. With the unification, the need arose for a common approach to the essence of the struggle, a definition of concepts, i.e. classifications. Apparently, as a result of this, a unified classification of judo wrestling techniques emerged, which became a guiding methodological document for judokas all over the world.

An important feature of this classification should be considered that the scope of the technique and its content are strictly defined (forty techniques in total). Each technique has its own number (according to what category of difficulty was recognized for this technique at that time) and its own name.

The clarity and simplicity of the classification, which unites only forty techniques with specific names, has a significant advantage - a small list of techniques facilitates the organization of the educational process.

It should be noted that almost all groups of modern wrestling techniques are represented in the Japanese classification.

However, when analyzing the classification, it is most important to establish the correctness of the characteristic by which equipment was divided into sections and subsections.

From this point of view, the Japanese classification cannot be considered successful.

Japanese experts of that time divided the entire volume of judo fighting techniques into three large sections, which, literally translated, are called as follows:

- ✓ the art of throwing while standing;
- ✓ the art of throwing in a prone position;
- ✓ the art of throws in a body-to-body position.

Each of the three sections was further divided into subsections.

1. The art of throwing while standing:

- ✓ hand technique;
- ✓ hip technique; – foot technique.

2. The art of throwing in a prone position: – with your back to the mat; - sideways to the carpet.

3. The art of throwing in a body-on-body position (corresponds to the modern concept of “parterre”): – the art of holding;

- ✓ the art of strangulation;
- ✓ the art of painful techniques.

Each of these subsections contains a small list of techniques that, according to Japanese experts, are similar to each other.

When analyzing the first section, it is clear that the division into subsections is based on the sign of the attacker’s action in a standing position with individual parts of the body (arms, hips, legs). First of all, it should be noted that not a single wrestling technique can be performed only with the arms, only with the hips, or only with the legs. We can only talk about the predominant participation of individual parts of the body. With this division, actions by individual parts of the body are included in other subsections as equal units. So, in all three subsections there are throws with a twist (according to modern terminology). In particular, the same throw - a turn-up by grabbing the lapel and sleeve - is available in two groups (in the second and third). The only difference is that in one case it is performed with the predominant participation of the hips (then it belongs to the second group), and in the other - with the predominant participation of the legs (then it is classified as the third group). This confirms the unsuccessful choice of feature.

The second section is unsuccessful in that the throws included in it are performed not from a prone position, but from a standing position. The name of the section, apparently, is dictated by the desire of the classifiers to separate throws into a separate group, after which the attacker maintains a standing position. However, such a division is artificial. This attribute is not a sufficient basis for dividing the standing throwing technique into two independent sections.

The third section of the Japanese classification of judo fighting techniques contains three subsections: “the art of holding”, “the art of suffocation”, “the art of painful holds”.

The major elements of this section are presented logically. Each subsection is separate from the others in content. The section as a whole combines techniques for performing holds, chokes and painful holds in all possible positions of wrestlers.

The imperfection of the Japanese classification of judo fighting techniques is expressed in its limitations. For example, the second and third subsections of the third section are presented only in the form of a list of individual techniques with specific names. A number of techniques combined by Japanese specialists and included in the general list of technical actions are not included in the classification scheme. Apparently, the compilers of the classification were unable to find their main features necessary for classification.

It should also be noted that the presence of only forty throws in the standing position imposes restrictions on the actions of the wrestlers and, thus, leads to an impoverishment of the wrestling technique.

Systematic physical activity of a certain direction, periodic extreme effects on the body significantly expand the range of adaptive mechanisms, form a complex of special adaptive characteristics that have a specific morphofunctional content.

Rapid growth of the body in length negatively affects the manifestations of complex movements in which the child's entire body is involved, but does not significantly affect the accuracy of manual actions. As the body develops and acquires motor experience, abilities and skills, correlations between indicators of various manifestations of motor actions with a changing situation significantly decrease, which makes it possible to talk about a certain age-related increase in the specificity of individual manifestations of motor abilities.

At the first stage, scientific and methodological literature on the problem under study was studied and analyzed. At the second stage of the study, an experimental test was carried out to test the effectiveness of the proposed individual methodology, introduced into the educational and training process of young judokas at the stage of initial sports specialization. At the third stage, analyzes were given to the morphofunctional indicators of young judokas, depending on the development of special physical qualities.

To summarize, it must be said that from the point of view of classification theory, the Japanese classification of judo fighting techniques is an attempt to create a multi-level classification scheme. However, this is true for the top two levels. Further, in all sections and subsections of the classification, the technique is presented in the form of lists of special names meaning specific techniques. Due to the limited number of techniques, they cannot be arranged in order of increasing difficulty. In addition, ready-made lists of specific names of techniques, no matter how fully they reflect ideas about judo technique, cannot replace what in classification theory is called the key to constructing names.

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